

Report on Urban heat in the Nordic countries with examples from Oslo and Norway

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Introduction

Increasing heatwaves¹, with prolonged episodes of abnormally high temperatures, are one of the major climate change related risks in Europe (European Climate Risk Assessment, 2024). Even though climate change models do not predict heatwaves to become a major climate risk in the Nordic countries, heatwaves have become twice as likely to appear due to changes in the climate (Holmgren & Kjellström, 2024) and the relative increase of events with high temperatures can have an impact on public health.

Indeed, during the European heatwave of 2018, the Nordic countries experienced a long period of above normal temperatures after a warm and dry spring, resulting in drought and wildfires. In May, the heatwave was centered on southern Norway and Sweden where the temperatures were 6 - 7°C above average (up to 30°C). Above average temperatures were also detected over all of Finland. In June, the temperatures were, in average, above normal in Denmark, but in Norway, Sweden, and Finland, the temperatures were average. July 2018 was again characterized by large positive temperature anomalies over large parts of northern Europe. The temperature anomalies were largest over northern Finland as well as over large parts of Sweden and Norway where they exceeded 5°C (up to 32°C) (Sinclair et al., 2025). Norway had many occurrences of heatwaves, especially in the more populated southern and eastern parts of the country where some areas had over 40 occurrences (Tilley Tajet, 2020).

During May to August, Swedish weather stations recorded ≥ 50 days ≥ 25 °C (Holmgren & Kjellström, 2024) and a study found that a large part of the over 600 excess deaths in Sweden of the summer of 2018, could be attributed to the high temperatures (Åström et al., 2019). A rich body of evidence confirms the impacts of heatwaves on people's health, from relatively mild symptoms such as fatigue and worsening general condition, to serious consequences such as heatstroke and death (*Hälsoeffekter av värmeböljor – En kunskapssammanställning*, 2022). In general, the vulnerability to heat is higher in young children, older adults (people over 65 years old), and chronically ill individuals (Broczek, 2021; *Hälsoeffekter av värmeböljor – En kunskapssammanställning*, 2022) as well as people living alone or without social contacts.

Also, several studies of outdoor conditions during heatwaves show that mortality is higher in urban areas due to the Urban Heat Island effect (UHI) that is maintaining a high nighttime temperature (Iodice et al., 2024; Lundgren Kownacki et al., 2019). Urban heat islands develop when buildings and asphalt absorb and store heat that increases the

¹ In this report, we follow the interdisciplinary conceptualization of heat(waves) in the EmCliC project “as simultaneously individual experiences, biophysical changes, and socio-political phenomena”, recognizing the complexity and multiplicity of the representation, management and experience of heatwaves by natural scientists, policy makers, and vulnerable groups, such as older adults (Boni et al., 2023).

surface temperature. Research on the spatial patterns of the UHI intensity in Oslo demonstrates that the city is already affected by UHI, with its intensity reaching up to 5.5° in some districts (Badach et al., 2025). In combination, the UHI in cities and the risk of more intense heatwaves, increases the risk of health effects due to increased heat and possible impact on public health and urban livability.

In 2023, the Norwegian Institute of Public Health, Folkhelseinstituttet (FHI), published a report on Vulnerability and adaptation needs in the health and care sector in Norway. The report is based on the results of a survey by FHI, that were consistent with the findings of previous, more general surveys. The report shows that only a minority of both local health authorities and state health institutions have implemented vulnerability assessments or adaptation measures for buildings, property and infrastructure. Even fewer, less than 10%, of respondents of the FHI survey, said that possible increased disease burden due to climate change was included in the vulnerability assessments and adaptation measures (*Klimaendringer*, 2023). The report concludes with:

“Possible changes in the burden of disease in the population related to climate change have not, or to a very limited extent, been considered in ongoing initiatives. This is probably due to little documentation and knowledge of the possible health consequences of climate change in Norway”. (*Klimaendringer*, 2023)

At the same time, a comparison and analysis of national climate change adaptation in the Nordic region by the Nordic Council of Ministers, demonstrates that much adoption-related knowledge exists in Norway, but that it tends to be fragmented and not translated into strategies and actions (Gram-Hanssen et al., 2023). The authors further argue that the Nordic countries have very good conditions for generating “state-of-the-art-research on climate change adaptation” and that it is a need to close the knowledge-action gap (Gram-Hanssen et al., 2023, p. 124).

Even if the Nordic region still enjoys relatively moderate summer conditions, the relative increase of events with high temperatures can have an impact on public health. Due to the excessive deaths in Sweden after the European heatwave 2018 and since more intense heatwaves are predicted in the Nordic countries, Åström et al. (2019) suggests that there are reasons for short- and long-term precautionary measures.

This report is part of the *EmCliC+ Societal Engagement* research activity, conducted as part of the bilateral initiative Science & Society, funded by the Norway and EEA grants 2014–2021 (grant no 2024/43/7/HS6/00002). EmCliC+ is a follow up research activity to a larger project “Embodying Climate Change. Transdisciplinary Research on Urban Overheating” (EmCliC), conducted in 2020-2024. The project studied older adults’ experiences of urban heat in Warsaw and Madrid. The research combined the perspectives of natural and social sciences, quantitative and qualitative methods, to

study the experiences and adaptation to urban heat as a biosocial phenomenon. While in EmCliC we focused on urban heat in southern and central-eastern Europe, in this report the focus shifts to the situation around urban heat, related risk and adaptation, in northern Europe.

The aim of this report is to investigate how prepared the Nordic countries (here defined as Norway, Sweden, Finland and Denmark) are for more abundant heatwaves and higher summer temperatures. This desk research analysis of policy solutions to urban heat and projected heat related risks focuses on the Nordic countries in general, and Norway and Oslo, in particular. Following an introduction to the risks associated with increased urban heat, I will report on how research predicts climate change in the Nordic countries and how mitigation and adaptation to these climate risks are regulated. After a more specific description of the predicted climate risks of Norway, I will present how Oslo municipality works with climate adaptation measures in general and give examples of policies for mitigating the risks of urban heat. The report will end with a reflection on the challenges and possibilities of the Nordic approach to climate change adaptation.

Climate change in the Nordic countries

The IPCC report on Climate Change 2022 described the risks of extreme urban heat as increasing in cities where heat is a risk already today. This does not include the Nordic countries (Bednar-Friedl et al., 2022).

Research on climate change describes climate risks in the Nordic countries as changes in temperature, precipitation, and wind (Walsh et al., 2020). A strong warming at high latitudes during winter season has already been observed in the Nordic region (Turesson et al., 2024, p. 10). Due to loss of sea ice, flooding, drought, wildfires (Turesson et al., 2024; Walsh et al., 2020), as well as an increase in the number of storms and extreme weather events (Turesson et al., 2024, p. 10) impacts are expected on ecosystems and infrastructure. There is also a risk of more frequent, more intense, and longer lasting heatwaves (Rutgersson et al., 2022) – even so, not comparable to the risks of extreme urban heat that is predicted for other parts of Europe.

Projections for climate in Norway up to year 2100 are presented in the report Climate in Norway (Hanssen-Bauer et al., 2017). The report highlights the effects of more intense and more frequent events of heavy rainfall, such as flooding. Predictions also include an increase of the annual temperature by ca. 4.5 °C (interval: 3.3 to 6.4 °C) with the largest increase in spring and winter. Even so, as can be seen in Figure 1, an increase in the number of “warm days”, with a daily mean temperature above 20 °C is estimated, from about 10 days today up to about 30 days in 2100 in the Oslo area (Hanssen-Bauer et al., 2017). The relative increase may have an impact on public health and urban livability in the Nordic countries.

Figure 1. The number of days (dager) with a daily average temperature above 20 °C in the period 2071-2100 according to RCP4.5 (left) and RCP8.5 (right) (Hanssen-Bauer et al., 2017).

Climate policies and adaptation measures

The climate goals, climate policies and their implementation in the Nordic countries are framed by climate laws and climate mitigation efforts that are aligned with the European Union’s targets for cutting greenhouse gas emissions. Climate policy in the Nordic countries also includes fiscal climate policy tools, such as energy and carbon taxes on fuels and industries (Tapia et al., 2022). The Nordic countries have long been considered front runners on Climate policy. However, it is argued that

“[...] climate change adaptation is happening too slowly, is often aimed at the climate of today as opposed to the climate of tomorrow and lacks the appropriate knowledgebase to estimate how climate change will affect society, and which measures are most effective in preventing unacceptable forms and levels of damage” (Gram-Hanssen et al., 2023, p. 10).

Even though health impacts of climate change are included in vulnerability reports, such as effects on morbidity and mortality due to heatwaves, most societal risks in relation to climate change in the Nordic countries is associated with loss, disruption or damage of roads and other critical infrastructure, and the losing of access to societal services, power outage, damage to property and agriculture (Turesson et al., 2024).

The urban areas in northern Europe (e.g. Oslo) are not yet as heavily affected but might be in the future. For example, a study on effects of high temperatures on hospital visits and mortality in Finland found that individuals with Alzheimer’s disease and dementia were one of the groups with higher effect on hospitalization and mortality. At the same time, they were unable to detect an elevated risk in the larger older population group.

Even though these findings indicate that protective measures were taken by the public health services (Astone & Vaalavuo, 2023). Sweden, Denmark and Finland have a focus on monitoring temperature and have warning-systems for heat (*Finnish Meteorological Institute -Information on Warnings, 2025; Varningar och meddelanden, 2025; Varsler om farligt vejr i Danmark, 2025*). Norway does not have alert systems for heat but have it for other weather conditions (*Farevarsler i Norge, 2025*). The Public Health Agency of Sweden, Folkhälsomyndigheten, also have guidelines for implementing action plans and information material for heatwaves (*Att hantera hälsoeffekter av värmeböljor - vägledning till handlingsplaner, 2022*). The guidelines give a short introduction to the health risks of heat and define vulnerable groups, such as older adults, before guiding organizations towards implementing a systematic approach with measures to minimize negative health effects (ibid). This includes identifying target groups, preparing information materials, testing routines, and designing an alarm chain for mediating heat alerts and instructions on designing measures (ibid).

The often referred to definition of a heatwave from the World Meteorological Organization, WMO, with more than five consecutive days of at least 5 over the normal maximum temperature (from the standard normal period 1961-1990) does not really work in colder climates since heatwaves may occur during winter. In Sweden, a heatwave (or “värmebölja” that directly translated from Swedish is a “warm wave”) is defined as a period of at least five consecutive days with a maximum daily temperature of at least 25°C (*Väderspråk, 2025*). In Finland, a hot day is when the daily highest temperature is above 25°C (*Atmosfär-ABC – Meteorologiska institutet, 2025*) and warnings to the public are sent out when the temperature is above 27°C, aiming to alert about increasing health risks (*Finnish Meteorological institute – Information on warnings, 2025*). In Denmark, there is a heatwave when the average of the highest recorded temperatures, measured over three consecutive days at the same location, exceed 28°C (*Hedebølge eller bare en varmebølge?, 2025*). A Danish “warm wave” is identical, but with mean temperatures exceeding 25°C, which is similar to the Swedish definition. Norway used the Danish definition of a heatwave but have since 2022 improved their own definition. Today, according to the Norwegian definition, a heatwave is five or more consecutive days where the maximum temperature is 27 degrees or higher (*Hetebølger, 2022*).

Due to its geographical diversity and challenging weather conditions, local authorities in Norway have a long history of adapting to natural hazards. Thus, in general, Norway is said to have a high adaptive capacity to address local climate risks, especially when it comes to natural hazard (Gram-Hanssen et al., 2023). On the national level, the Climate Act (Klimaloven, 2017) puts responsibilities on the government to prepare annual reports for the Parliament on how Norway is preparing for and adapting to climate change. Through the Planning and Building Act (Plan- og bygningsloven, 2008), municipalities, county municipalities and the state are required to contribute to preparing for and adapting to climate change through planning and other governmental and business

activities. In principle, the national level government responsibilities are mainly about enabling and coordinating cross-sectoral work, reporting, and creating a knowledge base on climate change to be used for guiding adaptation planning and implementation. As such, the Norwegian approach is rather decentralized.

Work on climate adaptation and vulnerability assessments in Norway has begun within several sectors, including under the auspices of The Norwegian Association of Local and Regional Authorities, KS (Kommunesektorens interesseorganisasjon) and The Norwegian Directorate for Civil Protection (Direktoratet for samfunnssikkerhet og beredskap, DSB). Much of this work is also relevant for climate adaptation in the health sector, especially regarding buildings, property and infrastructure. According to a report on need for adaptation measures in the health sector of Norway (Rødland et al., 2023), possible changes in the burden of disease related to climate change have not, or to a very limited extent, been considered in ongoing initiatives. This is probably due to the lack of documentation and knowledge about the possible health consequences of climate change in Norway. The path towards a low-emission and climate-adapted health system is in many areas similar to the adaptation work in other sectors, but the health sector must also consider an expected increase in the need for health care (Rødland et al., 2023).

The regional and especially the local level (the county governor, county municipalities, and municipalities) have the main responsibility to implement the climate policies. The municipalities have the overall responsibility for local adaptation planning and the practical implementation of adaptation measures.

Adaptation to climate risks in the Oslo area

The climate work in Oslo municipality is guided by five main goals in the Climate adaptation strategy (Klimatilpasningsstrategi for Oslo kommune, 2013). Four of them are mitigation measures to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, increasing the natural carbon layer in vegetation and soil, and reducing energy use within the municipality. One of the five goals is about strengthening Oslo's ability to withstand climate change and developing the city to be equipped for the changes expected towards 2100 (Klimatilpasningsstrategi for Oslo kommune, 2013).

A background report to the Oslo municipality Climate adaptation strategy highlighted the need for long-term planning as well as preparedness for acting on situations in relation to extreme precipitation, storm flooding, wind, landslides, wildfires (Klimatilpasning-Bakgrunnsdokument for Oslo Kommune, 2013). The website of Oslo municipality Climate adaptation strategy (*Klimatilpasningsstrategi - Miljø- og klimapolitikk*, 2016) lists water, land use, infrastructure, health, the natural environment, and preparedness as the focus areas of the climate strategy.

Linked to the Climate strategy, Oslo Municipality has adopted a climate budget (*Klimabudsjett Oslo kommune*, 2024) that addresses the adaptation goals from its Climate Adaptation Strategy, incorporating measures like urban greenery to enhance resilience. The municipal planning strategy for 2024–2027 (*Planstrategi 2024–2027 - Kommuneplan*, 2024) acknowledges the potential need to update the broader Climate Strategy as extreme weather events emerge. Urban heat is not specifically mentioned.

Listed below are some examples of Oslo municipality's approach to integrating climate adaptation and urban resilience into its municipal policies and urban planning initiatives. The list includes adaptation measures that directly or (most often) indirectly will affect urban heat impacts. Even though they are not primarily seen as urban heat adaptive measures, but rather adaptive measures for other natural hazards, such as heavy rainfall or flooding.

- **Natural Hazards Oversight:** An inter-agency resource group will continue monitoring natural hazard risks, advising planning and construction efforts to protect against both known and emerging threats.
- **Green Infrastructure:** The Action Plan for green roofs and building fronts (Byrådssak 178/23, 2023) argues that increasing urban greenery improves biodiversity, regulates the local microclimate during hot days, and reduces risks to life, infrastructure, and equipment from heat, drought, and flooding (Byrådssak 178/23, 2023).
- **Climate Smart Urban Design:** The Architectural Policy (*Arkitekturpolitikk for Oslo - Byutvikling*, 2018) emphasizes designing buildings and public spaces that are energy efficient and resilient to extreme weather by incorporating features like green roofs, rain beds, and water channels to enhance natural diversity and urban livability.

Challenges and possibilities

In Nordic cities like Helsinki, Stockholm, Oslo, and Copenhagen, the warming trend is beginning to expose vulnerabilities in decades-old urban designs. Historically, these cities prioritized insulation and thermal mass to cope with harsh winters. Unfortunately, those same features tend to trap heat during summer heatwaves, increasing the urban heat island (UHI) effect. Even if the Nordic region still enjoys relatively moderate summer conditions, the relative increase during extreme heat events can have an impact on public health and urban livability.

Nonetheless, the Norwegian Environmental Agency (Miljødirektoratet) write on their webpage that future higher temperatures and a possible increase in the number of heatwaves may result in health risks, but with a limited health impact in the coming decades. However, they further stress the importance of ensuring sun protection and

sufficient shade when planning for future buildings and land use (*Klimaendringer og helse*, 2024).

This is important since most buildings in the Nordic countries lack air conditioning. It is also important to consider possibilities of lower thermal thresholds for people living in the Nordic countries, meaning that they will get ‘too hot’ and the heat would affect their wellbeing and health at lower temperatures than for instance in southern Europe (Boni et al. 2023; (Hassani et al., 2024). There is thus a need to focus on heat problems in indoor environments due to the connection between the outdoor and the indoor climate in this type of buildings (Lundgren Kownacki et al., 2019). Several studies have further argued that the development of severe indoor heat levels is complex, due to also depending on the urban design (e.g., type of building, design/geometry, and building materials), the presence of urban greenery (Iodice et al., 2024; Leal Filho et al., 2018; Lundgren Kownacki et al., 2019; Stone et al., 2023) and different types of water features to provide cooling effects (Iodice et al., 2024; Leal Filho et al., 2018). The behavior and influence of the residents also affect indoor heat levels (Lundgren Kownacki et al., 2019).

Research on climate adaptation argues that the Nordic countries overall present a high adaptation capacity on a country-level (Greselin, 2022; Juhola et al., 2012). However, there are differences between countries (Juhola et al., 2012) and within each country, especially between urban and rural areas (Greselin, 2022). For example, local management does not perceive the risks of climate change as different or more urgent than already existing risks. Also, the use of existing risk management analysis does not capture the complexity of risks accompanied with climate change, such as urban heat (Kindberg, 2023; Rapeli & Mussalo-Rauhamaa, 2022; Witnes Karlson et al., 2024). For example, in a study on climate change adaptation in Halmstad, Stavanger, and Dordrecht, special adaptation, and precautionary measures in the two Nordic countries were managed with the interpretation of climate change as an amplifier of existing risks (Witnes Karlson et al., 2024). The authors further argue that such an approach limits the response to only existing threats, not considering for instance urban heat. A study from Finland, highlights that even though the regional and local levels of government are trying their best to alleviate impacts of heat, there are “major deficiencies in risk mitigation, preparedness and response to heatwaves in Finland” (Rapeli & Mussalo-Rauhamaa, 2022).

Despite the lack of specific policy adaptation measures for urban heat in the Nordic countries, the measures implemented to improve air quality and adapt to stormwater and flood-risks also have a positive effect on mitigating heat stress. More specifically, this involves focusing on nature-based solutions for adaptation measures, such as increasing urban greenery (Andersson-Sköld et al., 2015; Lindberg et al., 2016; Stone et al., 2023). Thus, even if heat is not recognized as an important risk, many of the implemented mitigation initiatives might also work for mitigating urban heat.

Older adults and other vulnerable groups

The Nordic approach to urban planning as welfare states is focused on sustainability and the quality of life. Yet, there seems to be a gap in knowledge in the Nordic countries on the socioeconomic impacts of climate policies on vulnerable groups (Tapia et al., 2022). For example, older adults with lower incomes and savings are expected to experience challenges in keeping their homes at a comfortable temperature if energy prices rise due to climate policies aiming for cutting greenhouse gas emissions (ibid). Similarly, people in vulnerable situations might be more affected by the negative consequences of urban heat as they cannot afford to install and use air-conditioning, or other measures to decrease the indoor temperature.

The risk of increased occurrence of heatwaves is prompting urban planners and public health officials to rethink traditional strategies. Health risks—especially for vulnerable populations, like older adults and those with preexisting conditions—are mounting as city infrastructures struggle to adapt. Insights from research (e.g. the EmCliC and EmCliC+ Societal engagement projects) stress that integrated indoor/outdoor evaluations are essential. Research recommends a combined approach that considers both building design (such as window placement and insulation) and the enhancement of outdoor measures, such as green spaces, and shaded areas, to effectively mitigate summer heat stress (Iodice et al., 2024; Lundgren Kownacki et al., 2019). Research also recommends a holistic approach to climate policies in order to minimize negative effects on vulnerable groups by not addressing climate impacts in isolation – but rather make them go hand in hand with other measures (Tapia et al, 2022).

However, research on social impacts of climate policy demonstrates that the Nordic model could provide a sustainable model for reacting to climate change related threats due to already intervening in response to social risks, reducing vulnerability and providing social protection (Greselin, 2022; Pilli-Sihvola et al., 2018).

Is there a need to shift climatic realities in the Nordics?

Historically, the Nordic cities prioritized insulation and thermal mass to cope with harsh winters. Unfortunately, those same features tend to trap heat during summer heatwaves, exacerbating the urban heat island (UHI) effect.

Due to climate change, the Nordic countries can expect more intense precipitation and higher temperatures in winter. Most societal risks in relation to climate change are thus associated with loss, disruption or damage of infrastructure and the loss of access to societal services, power outage, damage to property and agriculture (Turesson et al., 2024). Therefore, and as was seen in the Oslo example, most of the climate adaptation measures focus on mitigating risks through cutting greenhouse gas emissions and adapting the built environment and infrastructure through planning measures. However, there seems to be a need to take a more holistic approach to climate risks in the Nordic

countries. Even if the region still enjoys relatively moderate summer conditions, a relative increase in extreme heat events will have an impact on people's lives and wellbeing.

The heat adaptation measures in the Nordic countries seem to focus on nature-based solutions that will mitigate the negative effects of several climate risks. This is a good starting point but rising temperatures and increasingly frequent heatwaves are now presenting new challenges that demand creative, forward-looking solutions.

It is thus time for the Nordic countries to speed up climate change adaptation measures aimed at the climate of tomorrow instead of the climate of today. There is also a need to establish an appropriate knowledgebase on how climate change and increased heat will affect society and how to best mitigate negative effects on public health and urban livability (Gram-Hanssen et al., 2023). There might also be a need to complement the national level focus on mitigating greenhouse gases with a stronger focus on societal adaptation to climate risks. This would support the decentralized approach and make the climate change adaptation measures on the regional and local levels more coherent.

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